

right stridulating organs on glass microslides using Hoyer's medium. Morphometric measurements were made at the 100x objective of a phase contrast microscope fitted with a linear, graduated ocular micrometer. Calibrated micrometer units were converted into microns.

The petal-like sclerites were smaller in

males than in females in both rice- and weed-infesting BPH, but the rice insects possessed significantly shorter and wider sclerites than those on *Leersia* (see table). The number and length of chitinous scales in males and the length of chitinous scales in females of both rice BPH and *Leersia* BPH differed

significantly. Males had significantly fewer and smaller chitinous scales than females.

Thus, variations in acoustic signals between the two sympatric populations of BPH can be attributed to morphometric differences in their stridulating organs.□

Dimensions of petal-like sclerite, and the number and size of chitinous scales on the sclerite in males and females of *N. lugens* infesting rice (RBPH) and *L. hexandra* plants (LBPH).^a IIRRI, 1988.

Sex	Sclerite dimension						Chitinous scales on petal-like sclerite								
	Length (μ)			Width (μ)			Number			Length (μ)			Width (μ)		
	RBPH	LBPH	Difference	RBPH	LBPH	Difference	RBPH	LBPH	Difference	RBPH	LBPH	Difference	RBPH	LBPH	Difference
Male	103 b	112 b	-9**	57 b	49 b	8*	117 b	99 b	18**	11 b	10 a	1**	6 b	5 b	1 ns
Female	141 a	133 a	8**	72 a	61 a	11**	125 a	125 a	0 ns	13 a	10 a	3**	7 a	6 a	1 ns

^aAv of 20 specimens of each sex. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. **, *, and ns = significant at 1% level, 5% level, and no significant differences by LSD test.

Carbofuran-induced rice leaf older (LF) resurgence

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LF (*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*) is a major pest of rice in the Sambalpur district of Orissa. We evaluated five insecticides against this pest in a field trial during the 1988 wet season. Susceptible Jaya was transplanted in 20-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Locally recommended

Effect of insecticides on LF control in rice.^a Sambalpur, Orissa, India, 1988 wet season.

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Damaged leaves (no./plant)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Cartap 4G	1.5	1.5	4.6
Carbofuran 3G	1.0	33.0	3.6
Ethoprofos 10G	1.0	10.9	4.0
Decamethrin + buprofezin (Dadeci 5.9 EC)	0.09	5.8	4.2
Phosalone 35 EC	0.5	9.2	3.8
Untreated check	—	20.4	3.5
LSD (0.05)		11.2	0.6

^aMean of 4 replications.

chemical fertilizers were applied at 10 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

LF damage was high at heading. At 85 DT, leaves with at least one-third of the leaf area damaged were removed from random-selected 20 hills in each

plot. Plots treated with carbofuran had higher leaf damage than the check plot (see table), perhaps indicating LF resurgence. All other treatments had lower LF damage. Cartap was most effective in controlling LFs.□

Incidence of two grain suckers in irrigated and upland rice

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Of the insect pests that attack rice in West Africa, internal stem feeders (lepidopterous and dipteran stem borers) cause the most damage; grain sucking bugs are next in importance.

Among the 15 species of grain suckers known, *Aspavia armigera* F. (Pentatomid) and *Stenocoris claviformis* Ahmad (Coreid) are important. Damaged grains have diffuse brown spots at the point of feeding. Heavily damaged grains are either empty or only partially filled.

The adult *Aspavia* is brown with a yellow spot at each corner of the

triangular shield. Its prothoracic plate has a pointed projection at each side of the dorsal side. The *Stenocoris* is similar in appearance to the Asian grain sucking bug *Leptocoris*.

We studied the relative abundance of these two species in irrigated and upland rice.

For irrigated rice, 21-d-old seedlings of ITA212 were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in a 50- × 50-m plot. For upland rice, ITA235 was dibbled at 4-5 seeds spaced 25 × 25 cm. Plot size was 50 m². Both crops were planted in mid-June 1986. Management practices followed standard recommendations. Sampling with 10 net sweeps per plot at 10 d intervals started at 50 d after transplanting (DT) and continued to 100 d.

In irrigated rice, more *Stenocoris* were found up to 80 DT (see figure). At 90 and 100 DT, the *Aspavia* population